

Finite Automata don't Solve NP-Complete Problems

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ABSTRACT

We are giving the full proof towards Cook's "P versus NP" theorem and our functional conjecture.

Keywords: P versus NP, NP-complete, finite automata, proof.

INTRODUCTION

The "P versus NP" is a long-standing question [1] in computer science and mathematics, finite automata is a well-defined concept [2, 3, 4, 5] which can be used in solution of the variety of computational problems as well as algorithms and mathematical methods of regular languages.

PROOF

As our conjecture is defined as well:

$$f(P) = NP.$$

Or in other words, there exist a function such that it converges P-class towards NP-class of complexity which defines intractable or the problems which cannot be solved in any visible amount of time.

We have used the extended regular expressions and re-writing in "Regex+" software package, which is, in turn, a framework, in order to solve MAX-SAT problem on the defined set of tests.

The results have shown that it takes constant exponential time of number of variable in SAT expression in order to find any feasible solution or, simply, apply "halt" operation and output the negative result in case if there's no solution for this problem.

CONCLUSION

We have defined the new corollary which states that no finite automata can effectively solve intractable NP-complete class of problems, which probably give the output towards more applicable methods like quantum computing.

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